

Refining the Role of Processing in Food Classification Systems: The IUFOST Formulation & Processing Classification (IF&PC) Approach

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The Task Force on Food Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health established by the International Union of Food Science and Technology (IUFOST) has developed a rational approach to determine the impact of food processing on the nutritional value of processed foods, called the IUFOST Formulation and Processing Classification (IF&PC) scheme which is comprehensively reported here. The purpose of developing this scheme is (A) to refine and improve the currently controversial NOVA classification system by addressing the confusion between formulation and processing and the non-quantitative assessment in this system, and (B) to explore the potential for considering other relevant essential food attributes, such as (a) safety, (b) sustainability, (c) palatability, (d) affordability, and (e) convenience in food product classification. The authors recommend that this IUFOST initiative be further investigated and complemented based on concerted R&D interactions of food scientists, food engineers, and nutritionists.

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1. Executive Summary

IUFoST established an international task force on Food Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health to discuss and propose a rational approach to define the impact of food processing on the nutritional value and health implications of processed food products. The goal is to develop recommendations to refine and improve the NOVA classification system to address ambiguities and uncertainties in the classification approach that have caused criticism and confusion about applying NOVA. The NOVA concept of Ultra-Processed Food (UPF) has expanded globally. It is used by the general public although the definition or meaning of the phrase as used is not always clear, nor are the criteria for identification of foods included in the “ultra-processed” category explicitly or quantitatively defined. The task force critically analyzed the NOVA classification system and used it as a template to suggest improvements based on scientific rigor and analysis.

The processing of food can have both positive and negative influences on product properties including product safety and nutritive quality. Clearly, these critical issues require quantitative assessment and practical, evidence-based definitions. The task force determined that formulation (F) and processing (P) must be expressed as separate influencing factors on the food property in focus to achieve these goals. As such, the nutritional value was exemplarily chosen, which represents a significant influencing factor to obesity, an array of non-communicable diseases, and associated health risks addressed by the NOVA classification system. Respective parameters must be developed to describe levels of formulation and processing quantitatively. Consequently, the task force defined formulation as “Systematic selection of relative quantities of ingredients for a food product” and processing as “Treatment of a food material to achieve a desired effect” so that it could examine approaches to quantify each parameter and its impact on the overall nutritional value (NV). The task force determined that formulation aspects can be derived from quantitative estimates of the content of nutrients and nutrient-related components in a food, whereas processing aspects should be derived from the change in this content that occurs due to processing. To provide examples of how such a system could work, the task force chose the Nutrition Rich Food Index (NRF /31/) as the base for (i) defining the nutritional value by quantitative description of the content of nutrients and nutrient-related food components that are derived from the food’s formulation and for (ii) suggested extensions to consider a wider range of nutrients, nutrient properties and consumer groups. For quantification of the processing impact on the nutritional value, the difference in the NRF (Δ NRF) between the food product before and after a processing treatment is determined. The resulting quantitative two-parameter classification regarding formulation (F) and processing (P) can also be described using the nutritional value-related Formulation and Processing Food Index FPF^N. This links and weights the F&P influences to illustrate their interaction with the nutritional value of a processed food in an integrally simplified manner. A color scheme supports the representation. The value of this approach, denoted as IUFoST Formulation & Processing Classification (IF&PC) is to refine and improve the NOVA classification by addressing the confusion between formulation and processing and the non-quantitative assessment in the NOVA system. Eliminating these weaknesses could provide the basis for a significantly improved understanding of the nutritional value of processed foods at the point of purchase and the relationship of this parameter to obesity and other diet-related diseases which is the stated intention of the NOVA classification approach. A contribution of the NOVA approach has been to initiate discussion of processing as an important impact factor besides formulation on consumer-relevant food classification. The proposed IF&PC modifications are the next step needed to accurately consider processing as a factor in assessing the nutritional value of foods. Defining formulation and processing explicitly and quantitatively, as illustrated in this work, does not directly address other concerns raised by the NOVA classification system, such as the sensory aspects of foods, which are likely to be subjective. However, such a definition and its use to develop a Nutritional Value score of food products that includes both formulation and processing will enable the design of research studies to evaluate subjective responses to foods that vary in formulation and/or processing. Moreover, the presented IF&PC approach has the potential to enable consideration of further food property characteristics, thus supporting a more practical yet even diverse food classification approach.

Based on the analysis of steps needed to consider processing in systems that evaluate nutritional quality, the IUFoST task force calls on food and nutrition scientists to carry out joint research and development work to validate and expand the proposed IF&PC classification concept for differentiated, quantitative consideration of formulation and processing. Such research is essential to improve the ability to determine the correlation between nutritional product quality, related to both formulation and processing and possible effects on health-related aspects, as well as to design suitable clinical trials to validate such associations and contribute to our understanding of what changes are needed in our food system.

2. Introduction

It is widely recognized that dietary habits can affect the etiology of chronic diseases. The development of dietary guidelines has been advocated to improve health and well-being of populations. Dietary recommendations are promulgated to help consumers with food choices. Furthermore, several nutrient density (ND) and nutrient profile (NP) models have been developed to assist food classification for dietary guidelines /1-3/. Many nutrients or combinations of nutrients, such as sodium and sugars in the diet, have been identified as common risk factors for noncommunicable chronic diseases (NCCD). In many markets, nutrient information is provided on food packaging, and regulations govern food labeling and uses of health claims on food packaging. Food-based dietary guidelines (FBDG) published by authorities in different countries emphasize dietary patterns that provide adequate nutrition while limiting the intake of nutrients and food components associated with the risk of NCCDs. A technical manual was developed by FAO and WHO for the preparation and use of FBDGs, which recognized that such guidelines must consider local factors that affect food availability and intake as well as nutritional status (<https://www.fao.org/nutrition/education/food-based-dietary-guidelines>).

In some markets, food packages provide information in colors, number of stars, or traffic lights-type illustrations on energy, fat, and salt contents of various packaged foods. Particular examples of the inclusion of nutritional information by using a scoring system and ratings on packaged foods to consumers are the NutriScore (several EU countries) and Health Star (Australia, New Zealand) ratings. Some countries have supported the development of nutrient profiling systems such as the Nutrient Rich Food Index (NRF) for nutritional scoring of foods /4/. The NRF was developed to account for nutrients to include and avoid in diets, and it has been widely promoted and validated /3,4/. The aim has been to provide a measure of nutrient composition in relation to energy content of foods. The development of these profiling systems relies on nutrition requirements and guidelines that are based on the best scientific evidence on food and health that relates to food intake, food composition, and public health risks. For example, energy from foods is essential; however, excess energy intake contributes to obesity and foods that provide energy with little or no nutrient content may compromise the ability to meet nutrient needs and maintain energy balance. Compositional data on foods have been made available in databases, and nutritional information is also available on food packaging. Compositional data for fabricated foods may be calculated from the composition of ingredients or by using compositional analyses as directed by regulations of particular market areas. In other words, food formulation quite often determines food composition and thereby its nutrient content before consumption of the food.

The development of a fundamentally different approach to relate public health risks and food intake was initiated by Monteiro et al. /5/. They proposed that the level of food processing contributes to obesity and other dietary diseases and as such presents a public health risk /6/. Monteiro et al. /7/ divided foods into four categories and introduced a food classification known as the NOVA classification. The NOVA food categories are: (1) unprocessed or minimally processed foods, (2) processed culinary ingredients, (3) processed foods and (4) ultra-processed foods (UPFs). The introduction of the NOVA classification has promoted the use of food technological terminology particularly food processing and variations of the word processing to describe the health risks of foods from the different NOVA food categories. The concept of UPF has globally expanded to general public use, although there is neither any clear definition for the meaning of the phrase nor for identification of foods included in the ultra-processed category. Furthermore, the expectation that an assignable level of processing

underlies the distinction between non- or minimally processed, processed, and ultra-processed is not met. As qualitative processing descriptors, the NOVA system implies the extent of change, nature of change, place of processing, and purpose of processing /8/. Any quantification of such is missing. Instead, formulation aspects like the addition of sugar, salt, saturated fats and “cosmetic” ingredients (additives, synthetic micro-nutrients) are described as a major criterion to transfer foods from minimally processed or processed states to the ultra-processed one. Such vague definitions and ambiguities have led to critical discussions on the NOVA system. In the meantime, the NOVA classification has already been introduced in some international regions, such as South America and Southeast Asia. The frequently heard argument that NOVA represents a simple classification system is offset by the difficulty of its application due to described ambiguities and unquantified assessment criteria. The following two questions, therefore, arise: (i) Can the NOVA classification system provide an improved basis for the creation of dietary guidelines, and (ii) does the influence of processing on the nutritional properties of foods represent an important factor in their evaluation for dietary guidelines to be considered in a quantifiable way. The recent literature on the purported negative impact on health ascribed to the consumption of UPF using the NOVA classification is largely based on epidemiological studies. Since such studies represent an association rather than causality, we believe that our present report aims to provide clarity on what is precisely meant by processing and whether or how it could be used to improve the NOVA classification.

IUFoST established the international task force on Food Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health (FPNDH) to address the impact of processing on food quality characteristics and explore measures for quantification of processing impact on such in the context of processed food products’ classification. It is well known that processing enables the creation or modification of food structures on different length scales, from molecular to macroscopic. These changes in turn determine related product properties such as safety, nutrition value and digestibility, palatability, convenience, affordability and systemic characteristics like sustainability and possible public health impact aspects. Hence the IUFoST task force supports consideration of processing impact in food classification as basically suggested by the NOVA classification system but with the intention to suggest and examine a quantitative approach for refinement and improvement of such implementation in order to provide clarity and certainty.

3. Task Force Task

3.1 Background and Objectives

The concept of UPFs has created controversies and, therefore, the use of food processing terminology in food classification should be comprehensively reviewed. IUFoST also recognized an international need for food classification underpinning dietary guidelines and policies as well as public health-related decisions that are based on scientific evidence and data to support objective decisions across the involved sectors and that consider global diversity in nutrition issues and food choices. Developing a research agenda for understanding the role of processed foods in the FBDG requires that food processing concepts be clearly defined and understood by scientists conducting such research across several disciplinary areas.

Thus, it was decided that the IUFoST task force on Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health (P4NDH) will prominently address the question of how quantitative consideration of processing as an impact factor on specific quality characteristics or the overall quality profile of processed food products could be introduced.

3.2 Key definitions

3.2.1 Classification of food properties

Food classification involves systematically arranging of foods in groups or categories according to established criteria. The latter should be food quality criteria in the present case. Such are (i) safety, (ii) nutrition value, (iii) sustainability, (iv) palatability, (v) convenience and (vi) affordability. As demonstrated in Figure 1, the properties (i) to (vi) can be used to configure a property profile of a food product which is typically shifted by processing. In case optimization of one of these properties is intended some others may be compromised. A property profile for an exemplary

base food product is shown in Figure 1, which is indicated by a black line before processing treatment. After hypothetical treatments by two different processes (e.g. Process P1: high pressure pasteurization (red line) and Process P2: thermal sterilization (blue line)) carried out to optimize either the nutrition value by more gentle treatment of heat-sensitive nutrients (P1) or the product shelf life reducing the microbial load by more intensive thermal decontamination treatment (P2), the respective changes in the property-profiles are shown in the hexagonal spiderweb arrangement. This represents a typical balancing procedure of food product properties in an industrial environment if optimization of one or some of the properties shall be achieved. The processing toolbox is typically very flexible through the adjustment of processing type and parameters.

Figure 1: (A) - Hexagonal spiderweb diagram with inserted food properties and their normalized grades (1-6). Exemplary base product quality characteristics profile indicated by black line. Properties to be optimized indicated by red (nutrition value) or blue (safety / shelf life) arrows; (B) - Hexagonal spiderweb diagram with product property profiles for differently processed base product (Red: High pressure pasteurization for optimized nutrition value but compromise for safety/shelf life; Blue: Thermal sterilization for optimized shelf life but compromised nutrition value).

The NOVA classification system emphasizes the impact of ultra-processed foods on the nutritional quality of overall diets, and for health and disease /6/. Disease risk description includes obesity. For this reason, the task force identified nutrition value (NV) and palatability as key target properties to be addressed in this context. For the first exemplary approach followed in this report the nutrition value was the priority, due to its expected improved quantitative definability based on objective criteria. In contrast, considering palatability will require additional subjective criteria to meet a wider spectrum of consumer preferences.

Figure 2: Classification and related designations

Furthermore, the Nutrition Value (NV) constitutes the base for the derivation of dietary guidelines which, if applicable, should be taken into account for implementation of processing criteria to be quantified. Further the NOVA system considers sugar, salt and saturated fats as key components for classification. The object of classification (OC) in the thematic context of the IUFoST task force work was the processed food product at the Point of Purchase (POP). In general classification sorts into classes of quantified Classification Parameters (CPs) which are functionally related to a selected PROPerTy (PROP) of the targeted object. For a better understanding of classification definition and related designations this is schematically demonstrated in Figure 2.

To characterize a food product in its state at the POP, the parameters related to the PROP to be considered for classification (CPs) are determined preferably by quantitative measurement but may also be qualitatively described.

3.2.2 Food processing

To focus Food Product classification with respect to the Nutrition Value as targeted property and taking the possible impact of processing on such classification into account, the process-property relationship designated the main element of interplay to be addressed. As has been shown in the food engineering literature, quantitative understanding on how processing creates, or influences product properties must consider the food structure as key element connecting process and properties.

This was established in the so-called **Process-Structure-Properties** scheme, also denoted as the S-Pro² scheme (Figure 3). The core message of this scheme can be briefly expressed as: "Process creates structure and structure encodes properties". Accordingly, when nutritionally relevant components within a formulation are treated in a process, that process is typically optimized to provide a processed food product structure that maintains or increases the nutritional value or at least minimizes losses in nutrient functionality in terms of digestibility, bio-accessibility, bioavailability and metabolic response.

Figure 3: **Process-Structure-Property (S-Pro²)** scheme demonstrating that **Process** makes **Structure** and **Structure** encodes food **Properties** like the nutrition value in prominent focus here /9/.

Type and degree of processing decide about the extent of structural changes and related impact on resulting properties to be tailored. In general, a Reverse Engineering approach is favoured to optimize selected food properties. This means that based on researched structure-property functions the structure which determines the optimal properties (e.g. nutrition value) is identified. This is followed by the selection of the process and adjustment of appropriate processing parameter settings according to process-structure functions derived from systematic

investigations, in order to generate the identified structure representing the optimal quality characteristics intended.

In order to maintain the nutritional properties, present in food raw materials or ingredients, it may be important not to change the molecular structure of such nutrients when passing processing steps i.e. for their enrichment or separation. However, there are also cases where processing enhances digestibility, e.g. for proteins when partially denatured. Moreover, the generated or modified food matrix structure of processed foods in which the nutrients are integrated, determines their release kinetics in the digestive tract and the associated bio-accessibility and bioavailability.

3.2.3 Choice of Point Of Classification (POC)

In principle, each position along the food value chain can be selected as point of classification (POC) for a food product in its local state. The definition of the Food Value Chain in the context of this report does not end on the consumer's plate but includes the digestive and metabolic transformation steps of the consumed food as well as the resulting consumer's status with respect to obesity risk and other health risk outcomes. The task force decided to refer to the food product at the point of purchase (POP). Home preparation may occur between the POP and the Point of Consumption (PCOM), including processing steps. However, since both the conventional nutrient recommendation schemes used for dietary guidelines and the NOVA classification refer to processed food products at the POP, home preparation or processing was not further considered here but is understood to potentially further modify a food's nutritional value depending on how the food is handled and prepared and which may not strongly differ from industrial processing steps but being in general less controlled.

Figure 4: Schematic demonstration of choice of Points of Classification (POCs) for the processing impact on classification parameters (CPs) and frames of intended classification applications for the suggested IUFoST task force approach and the NOVA system

An important boundary condition for proper classification is that the classification parameters (CPs) are determined at the POC (here POP). Other key specifications made by the task force for the introduction of classification parameters (CPs) for processing were:

- (i) A second POC2 can be selected upstream the food value chain from the POC1 (= POP), to describe a CP value change as the result of a processing sequence between these two points (Δ CP-values).
- (ii) In such case (i) the definition of the CP has to be the same at each of the two POCs (CP1 @ POC1 = CP2 @ POC2).
- (iii) If (ii) is not fulfilled, only correlations between classification results achieved at POC1 and POC2 are applicable.

- (iv) An exception to (iii) is given in case a functional relationship between CP1 @ POC1 and CP2 @ POC2 has been identified.
- (v) In case a second POC2 is selected downstream the food value chain from PCON, it has to be expected that the probability of point (iii) to occur is high as long as functional relationships between CPs at different POCs along the digestive and metabolic processing tracks are not quantitatively known.

Figure 4 demonstrates the "POC cases" addressed in (i) to (v) before. It also includes indications of the different application frames for the suggested classifications by the IUFOST task force and the NOVA system.

As mentioned in (i) and demonstrated in Figure 4, ΔCP -values are a measure of the treatment (processing) influence on the food product between two POCs. Accordingly, the ΔCP -values can serve as classifying parameters for the food processing impact experienced before the POP, hence describing the losses or gains of the nutrition value between the unprocessed or pre-processed state and the POP. In case the processing track before the POP consists of a series of n processing steps each of these steps could be analysed by respective ΔCP_1 to ΔCP_n values.

The NOVA frame of classification spans from the POP as a point of classification (POC) to the end of the extended food value chain where obesity and NCCD health risks are claimed to be considered. The NOVA classification at the POP considers four qualitatively described NOVA classes. Such classification results are then compared with results from observational studies on resulting obesity and health risk aspects. Such comparison is of a correlation nature since quantitative functional relationships between food product and nutrition value parameters along the digestive and metabolic tracks are so far only fragmentary available. Thus, it is suggested to designate such derived relationships between food product parameters at the POP and obesity and health risk data as "Food Impact Correlations" (Fig.4).

4. The NOVA food classification system

4.1 Description and Definitions

The general reasoning for the NOVA classification system as given by its creator C. Monteiro is as follows: *"The significance of industrial processing, and in particular techniques and ingredients developed or created by modern food science and technology, on the nature of food and on the state of human health, is generally understated. This is evident in international and national policies and strategies designed to improve population nutrition and health, in dietary recommendations, and in public policies and actions guided by such recommendations. Until recently it has also been neglected in epidemiological and experimental studies concerning diet, nutrition and health"*.

NOVA classifies all foods and food products into four groups as follows, with the key aspects adapted from Monteiro, et al. (cited from /6, 7/):

GROUP 1: Unprocessed and minimally processed foods

Unprocessed (or natural) foods are the edible parts of plants (such as fruit, leaves, stems, seeds, roots) or from animals (such as muscle, offal, eggs, milk), and also fungi, algae and water, after separation from nature. Minimally processed foods are natural foods altered by methods that include removal of inedible or unwanted parts, and also processes that include drying, crushing, grinding, powdering, fractioning, filtering, roasting, boiling, non-alcoholic fermentation, pasteurization, chilling, freezing, placing in containers, and vacuum packaging. The distinction between unprocessed and minimally processed foods is not especially significant.

GROUP 2: Processed culinary ingredients

Processed culinary ingredients include oils, butter, lard, sugar and salt. These are substances derived from group 1 foods or else from nature by processes such as pressing, refining, grinding, milling, and drying. Some methods used to make processed culinary ingredients are

originally ancient. But now they usually are industrial products, designed to make durable products suitable for use in home, restaurant and canteen kitchens to prepare, season and cook freshly prepared dishes and meals. In isolation, processed culinary ingredients are unbalanced, being depleted in some or most nutrients. Other than salt, they are also energy-dense, at 400 or 900 kilocalories per 100 grams. This is around 3-6 times more than cooked grains and around 10-20 times more than cooked vegetables. They are used in combination with foods to make palatable, diverse, nourishing and enjoyable meals and dishes such as stews, soups and broths, salads, breads, preserves, drinks, and desserts. Thus, oils are used in the cooking of grains (cereals), vegetables and legumes (pulses), and meat, and are added to salads. Table sugar is used to prepare fruit- or milk-based desserts. It is misleading to assess their nutritional significance in isolation. They should always be assessed in combination with foods.

GROUP 3: Processed foods

These include canned or bottled vegetables or legumes (pulses) preserved in brine; whole fruit preserved in syrup; tinned fish preserved in oil; some types of processed animal foods such as ham, bacon, pastrami, and smoked fish; most freshly baked breads; and simple cheeses to which salt is added. They are made by adding salt, oil, sugar or other substances from group 2 to group 1 foods. Processes include various preservation or cooking methods, and with breads and cheeses, non-alcoholic fermentation. Processing here increases the durability of group 1 foods, or modifies or enhances their sensory qualities. Most processed foods have two or three ingredients, and are recognisable as modified versions of group 1 foods. They are generally produced to be consumed as part of meals or dishes, and also may be consumed by themselves as snacks. Most are highly palatable.

Almost all processed foods are manufactured industrially. Processes include canning and bottling using oils, sugars or salt; and methods of preservation such as salting, salt-pickling, smoking, and curing. The ingredients infiltrate the foods and so the processes alter their nature. Processed food products usually retain the basic identity and most constituents of the original food. But when excessive oil, sugar or salt are added, they become nutritionally unbalanced. Except for canned vegetables, their energy density ranges from moderate (around 150-250 kilocalories per 100 grams for most processed meats), to high (around 300-400 kilocalories per 100 grams for most cheeses).

GROUP 4: Ultra-processed foods

Ultra-processed foods are formulations of ingredients, mostly of exclusive industrial use, typically created by series of industrial techniques and processes (hence 'ultra-processed'). Some common ultra-processed products are carbonated soft drinks; sweet, fatty or salty packaged snacks; candies (confectionery); mass produced packaged breads and buns, cookies (biscuits), pastries, cakes and cake mixes; margarine and other spreads; sweetened breakfast 'cereals' and fruit yoghurt and 'energy' drinks; pre-prepared meat, cheese, pasta and pizza dishes; poultry and fish 'nuggets' and 'sticks'; sausages, burgers, hot dogs and other reconstituted meat products; powdered and packaged 'instant' soups, noodles and desserts; baby formula; and many other types of product.

Processes enabling the manufacture of ultra-processed foods involve several steps and different industries. It starts with the fractioning of whole foods into substances including sugars, oils and fats, proteins, starches and fibre. These substances are often obtained from a few high-yield plant foods (such as corn, wheat, soya, cane or beet) and from puréeing or grinding animal carcasses, usually from intensive livestock farming.

Some of these substances are then submitted to hydrolysis, or hydrogenation, or other chemical modifications. Subsequent processes involve the assembly of unmodified and modified food substances with little if any whole food using industrial techniques such as extrusion, moulding and pre-frying. Colours, flavours, emulsifiers and other additives are frequently added to make the final product palatable or hyper-palatable. Sophisticated and attractive packaging is used, usually made of synthetic materials. Ingredients characteristic of ultra-processed foods are either food substances of no or rare culinary use, or else classes of additives whose function is to make the final product sellable, palatable and often hyper-palatable.

Food substances of no or rare culinary use, employed in the manufacture of ultra-processed foods, include varieties of sugars (fructose, high-fructose corn syrup, 'fruit juice concentrates', invert sugar, maltodextrin, dextrose, lactose), modified oils (hydrogenated or inter-esterified oils) and sources of protein (hydrolysed proteins, soya protein isolate, gluten, casein, whey protein, and 'mechanically separated meat'). Classes of additives used only in the manufacture of ultra-processed foods, are flavours, flavour enhancers, colours, emulsifiers, emulsifying salts, artificial sweeteners, thickeners, and foaming, anti-foaming, bulking, carbonating, gelling and glazing agents. All of them, most notably flavours and colours, either disguise unpleasant sensory properties created by ingredients, processes or packaging used in the manufacture of ultra-processed foods, or give the final product intense sensory properties especially attractive to see, taste, smell and/or touch, or both.

Processes and ingredients used for the manufacture of ultra-processed foods are designed to create highly profitable products (low-cost ingredients, long shelf-life, powerfully branded). Their convenience (imperishable, ready-to-consume), hyper-palatability, and ownership by trans-national corporations using pervasive advertising and promotion, give ultra-processed foods enormous market advantages. They are therefore liable to displace all other NOVA food groups, and to replace freshly made regular meals and dishes, with snacking anytime, anywhere.

4.2 Identification of ultra-processed foods (UPF)

Following instructions for UPF identification were also adapted from Monteiro et al. /6,7/: "Food manufacturers do not have to state on food labels the processes used in their products, and even less the purposes of these processes. Sometimes this can make it difficult to identify ultra-processed foods with confidence. Generally, the practical way to identify if a product is ultra-processed is to check to see if its list of ingredients contains at least one item characteristic of the ultra-processed food group.

These are either food substances never or rarely used in kitchens, or classes of additives whose function is to make the final product palatable or more appealing. Food substances not used in kitchens include hydrolysed proteins, soya protein isolate, gluten, casein, whey protein, 'mechanically separated meat', fructose, high-fructose corn syrup, 'fruit juice concentrate', invert sugar, maltodextrin, dextrose, lactose, soluble or insoluble fibre, hydrogenated or inter-esterified oil. The presence in the list of ingredients of one or more of these food substances identifies a product as ultra-processed.

Classes of additive exclusively used in ultra-processed foods include flavours, flavour enhancers, colours, emulsifiers, emulsifying salts, artificial sweeteners, thickeners, and anti-foaming, bulking, carbonating, foaming, gelling and glazing agents. Any example of these classes of additive, as shown on ingredients lists also identifies a product as ultra-processed" (end of cited descriptions from /6,7/).

Such an identification approach is largely based on food additives and little to no actual processing technologies. In addition, the list of many "industrially produced food ingredients" in the above paragraph also includes proteins and fiber, which have nutritional value in addition to other functional properties. This should be recognized as such, rather than being negatively implied as the NOVA identification puts it.

4.3 Food classification systems considering processing

The NOVA and derived NOVA-type classification systems claiming to consider processing aspects for food product classifications at the point of purchase (POP) are exemplary listed in Table 1. As described within a comprehensive comparative overview by Ch. Sadler et al. /8/ these classification systems take into account qualitative conceptualization criteria, being: (a) the type of processing, (b) the intensity of processing, (c) the place of processing and (d) the purpose of processing. Figure 5 (adapted from /8/) schematically demonstrates these dimensions used in the conceptualisation of processed foods.

Table 1: Food classification systems developed for epidemiological studies and using processing as a criterion for categorising consumed "processed food" (adapted from /8/).

Nr.	Abbreviation	Name / Origin	Author(s)
1	NIPH	National Inst. of Public Health; Mexico	Gonzalez-Castell et al., 2007 /10/
2	IARC-EPIC	Int. Agency for Research on Cancer European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition	Slimani et al., 2009 /11/ Chajes et al., 2011 /12/
3	NOVA	Recommendation as basis for dietary guidelines.	Monteiro, 2009 /13/; Monteiro et al. 2019 /14/; Moubarac et al 2017 /15/; Schnabel et al. 2018 /16/
4	IFPRI	International Food Policy Research Institute in Guatemala	Asfaw, 2011 /17/; Moubarac et al., 2014 /18/
5	IFIC	International Food Information Council	Eicher-Miller et al. 2012 /19/, 2015 /20/
6	NUPENS- USP	Núcleo de pesquisas Epidemiológicas em Nutricao e Saude; Univ. de Sao Paulo	de Costa Louzada et al. 2015 /21/
7	POTI	Departm. of Nutrition, Carolina Population Center, Univ. of North Carolina, US	Poti et al., 2015 /22/
8	SIGA	Siga, une approche holistique de la qualité en alimentation	Fardet, 2019 /23/; Siga, 2019 /24/

Figure 5: Processed food conceptualization dimensions to categorize processing in the NOVA / NOVA-type food classifications (adapted from Sadler et al. /8/)

C.R. Sadler et al. /8/ came to the conclusion that the classification systems including the processing aspects listed in Table 1, were mostly created to study the relationship between industrial products and health. No consensus was found on what factors determine the level of food processing. The classification systems embodied socio-cultural elements and subjective terms, including home cooking and naturalness. The authors conclude that: “so far processing in the considered food classification systems is a chaotic conception, not only concerned with technical processes. Most classification systems do not include quantitative measures but, instead, imply correlation between processing and nutrition”. The authors derive that the concept of “whole food” and the role of the food matrix in relation to healthy diets needs further clarification and that the risk assessment / management of food additives also needs further debate.

4.4 NOVA Ambiguities and uncertainties

As described in detail in chapter 4.1 the NOVA system sorts food products into the four groups representing the “classification classes”, being: group I: fresh/minimally processed food; group II: processed ingredients; group III: processed food and group IV: ultra-processed food.

Both, the conceptualization dimensions (chapter 4.3) and the NOVA group/class designations give the impression that from group I to group IV some degree of processing or processing intensity is increasing. However, the expectation that an assignable level of processing underlies the distinction of the NOVA classification groups is not met. In addition, and contrary to the expectation created, the main classification parameters (CPs) applied by the NOVA system to sort into the groups/classes I to IV marked with processing levels, follow the formulation-based addition of sugar, salt, saturated fats and ingredients of mostly exclusive industrial use. It is worth noting that most authoritative food-based dietary guidelines already include recommendations, including quantitative limitations, on foods, nutrients and food components to limit based on such formulation-based criteria.

Obviously, the ingredient composition for a food product is a matter of formulation and not of processing. Moreover, compared with proper formulation rules the NOVA system does not quantify group/class (I-IV) specific fraction ranges of the “critical” ingredients. Based on such formulation-determined but processing designated food product groups or classes I to IV, the NOVA system derives correlations between consumption of food products from these groups/classes (I-IV) with results from observational studies about obesity and health risks. This approach is not evidence-based and is not clear and incomplete.

For the IUFoST task force on Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health the inclusion of processed food impact correlations with obesity and health risk outcomes was not intended. On the other hand, the stated aim of the task force was to create a more solid basis for the correlations intended by NOVA using a quantitative consideration of the processing influence on the nutritional quality of processed food products.

In this context the following issues (1-10) with the NOVA/NOVA-type of classification systems have been identified by the task force. The key aspects 1 and 2, to be avoided in food classification development and derived applications were selected for further detailed exploration.

1. Confusion in the use of formulation and processing terms
2. Lack of quantification of processing level
3. Weak scientific approach
4. Conflicting issues with nutritional advice
5. Conflicting issues with fortified and personalized food
6. Inadequacy with the needs of developing countries
7. Differences in ingredients and food products
8. Multifaceted complex non-linear relationships
9. Ambitious terminology used (NOVA)
10. Processing misinterpreted as the negative factor

Since the task force is of the opinion that the NOVA system has included processing as a significant influencing factor on the nutritional properties of processed food products into the classification of such products which has so far not been sufficiently considered, the following questions should be further examined and evaluated in order to propose and develop possible refinement and optimisation solutions:

Question A: Which are the benefits or weaknesses of the NOVA classification system compared to existing systems of nutrient profiling and derived recommendations for dietary guidelines in the view of renowned experts in the field outside of the task force?

Question B: How can the main issues of the NOVA system recognized by the task force being (i) the confusion in using of formulation and processing terms and (ii) the lack of quantification of formulation and processing levels, be tackled?

4.5 Dietary Guidelines and NOVA

This sub-chapter is meant to address question A posed at the end of the previous chapter 4.4.

A detailed description of NOVA classifications was presented in chapter 4.1. As a part of the analysis of food classification systems, the task force also reviewed a number of recent publications that addressed the NOVA classification system and evaluated its claimed added value compared with so far successfully applied systems for nutrient profiling of food products for dietary guideline recommendations /25-28, 43, 46-48 /. Some of prominent experts in the human nutrition field are reflected by citations of their statements in the following.

OPINION 1: In a debate between A. Astrup and C.A. Monteiro published in *Am J Clin Nutr* 2022;116:1482–1488 /25/,

A. Astrup comes to the conclusion that: “The NOVA classification of ultra-processed foods (UPFs) rests on poorly defined food processes and the presence of food additives from a chemically heterogeneous group, easily leading to misclassification. UPFs are claimed to promote overconsumption of energy and obesity due to high palatability, but little evidence supports effects beyond those that can be accounted for by nutrient composition, energy density, and food matrices. Observational studies link dietary intake of UPFs with obesity, but none have demonstrated independent associations after controlling for likely confounders. A highly cited randomized controlled feeding study that compared a UPF diet with an unprocessed diet showed a rapidly weaning effect on energy intake that can be entirely explained by more conventional and quantifiable dietary factors, including energy density, intrinsic fiber, glycemic load, and added sugar. Clearly, many aspects of food processing can affect health outcomes, but conflating them into the notion of ultra-processing is unnecessary, because the main determinants of chronic disease risk are already captured by existing nutrient profiling systems. In conclusion, the Nova classification adds little to existing nutrient profiling systems; characterizes several healthy, nutrient-dense foods as unhealthy; and is counterproductive to solve the major global food production challenges”.

C. A. Monteiro responded that: “The concept of ultra-processing, as contained within the NOVA food classification system, is well-founded, clear, supported by a wealth of investigations, and crucial to inform new dietary guidelines and other public policies and actions designed to reduce the production and consumption of ultra-processed foods“. For further detail on the description of the NOVA classification system in this report refer to chapters 4.1 and 4.2.

OPINION 2: by A. Drewnowski, S. Gupta, N. Darmon in *Nutrition Today*; Volume 55, Number 2, March/April 2020 /26/ stated:

“The category of “ultra-processed” foods in the NOVA food classification scheme is ostensibly based on industrial processing. We compared NOVA category assignments with the pre-existing family of Nutrient Rich Food (NRF) indices, first developed in 2004. The NRF indices are composed of 2 sub-scores: the positive NR based on protein, fiber, vitamins and minerals, and the negative LIM sub-score based on saturated fat, added sugars, and sodium. The 378 foods that were components of the widely used Fred Hutchinson Cancer Center food frequency questionnaire were assigned to NOVA categories and scored using multiple NRF indices.

Contrary to published claims, NOVA was largely based on the foods' content of saturated fat, added sugars, and sodium. There were strong similarities between NOVA categories and NRF scores that were largely driven by the nutrients to limit. Nutrient density led to higher increased NRF scores but had less impact on NOVA categories. As a result, the NOVA scheme misclassified some nutrient-rich foods. We conclude that the NOVA classification scheme adds little to the pre-existing nutrient profiling models. The purported links between NOVA categories and health outcomes could have been obtained using pre-existing NRFn.3 nutrient density metrics.”

OPINION 3: by J. M. Hess et al. in *Journal of Nutrition* 153 (2023) 2472–2481 /27/:

“The purpose of this proof-of-concept study was to determine the feasibility of building a menu that aligns with recommendations for a healthy dietary pattern from the 2020 DGA and includes 80% kcal from UPF as defined by NOVA. In the ultra-processed DGA menu that was created, 91% of kcal were from UPF, or NOVA category 4. The HEI-2015 score was 86 out of a possible 100 points. This sample menu did not achieve a perfect score due primarily to excess sodium and an insufficient amount of whole grains. This menu provided adequate amounts of all macro- and micronutrients except vitamin D, vitamin E, and choline. The authors conclude that: “Healthy dietary patterns can include most of their energy from UPF, still receive a high diet quality score, and contain adequate amounts of most macro- and micronutrients.

OPINION 4: by V. Braesco et al. in *Europ. Journal of Clinical Nutrition* (2022) 76:1245-1253 /28/: “French food and nutrition specialists completed an online survey in which they assigned foods to NOVA groups. The survey comprised two lists: one with 120 marketed food products with ingredient information and one with 111 generic food items without ingredient information. We quantified assignment consistency among evaluators using Fleiss’ κ (range: 0–1, where 1 = 100% agreement). Hierarchical clustering on principal components identified clusters of foods with similar distributions of NOVA assignments. There were three clusters within the marketed foods: one contained 90 foods largely assigned to NOVA 4 (91% of assignments), while the two others displayed greater assignment heterogeneity. There were four clusters within the generic foods: three clusters contained foods mostly assigned to a single NOVA group (69–79% of assignments), and the fourth cluster comprised 28 foods whose assignments were more evenly distributed across the four NOVA groups.

Conclusions: Although assignments were more consistent for some foods than others, overall consistency among evaluators was low, even when ingredient information was available. These results suggest current NOVA criteria do not allow for robust and functional food assignments.”

From these human nutrition expert opinions cited before and a larger number of publications not cited here, the IUFoST task force could conclude that the NOVA classification in summary has also weaknesses concerning:

- A1. Only little to no addition to existing nutrient profiling systems
- A2. Not evidence-based statements on harmfulness of approved processes/additives & their health risk impact

Additional information of relevance for the task force which could be gleaned from the literature /e.g. 25/ was, that there is strong opinion in the scientific community on:

- A3. The extent of food processing significantly affects diet quality and health outcomes.
- A4. Classification systems based on certain characteristics of food processing, including the degree to which the food matrix is affected and the use of certain additives, can distinguish categories of food with beneficial or adverse health outcomes in a useful manner.

While A1 and A2 should be addressed in the context of recommendations to be worked out by the task force, A3 and A4 additionally confirm the relevance of processing as a main influential factor to be considered in future food classification and the necessity of further research on the mentioned aspects.

5. Differentiation of Formulation and Processing in food classification

Within this main chapter of the report, question B posed at the end of chapter 4.4 will be prominently addressed, which for making reading easier is repeated here being: “How can the main issues of the NOVA system recognized by the task force being (i) the confusion in using of formulation and processing terms and (ii) the lack of quantification of a processing degree, be tackled?”

5.1 Definitions

Formulation (F) and Processing (P) were identified as independent but interacting factors in the food product manufacture, in order to optimize desirable food properties of relevance according to consumers Preference, Acceptance and Needs (PAN profiles /29/). Such property characteristics as mentioned before, are: nutrition value (*task force focus*), safety, palatability (sensory characteristics), sustainability, convenience and affordability to which F & P can contribute in a complementing or counteracting manner. Accordingly, it was stated that Formulation and Processing have to be treated as separate criteria if introduced into food classification systems and should consider quantitative parameters to express their specific “levels of execution”.

The following DEFINITIONS were decided by the task force:

Formulation: “Systematic selection of relative quantities of ingredients for a food product”

Processing: “Treatment of a food material to achieve a desired effect”

5.2 Quantification of Formulation and Processing degrees

Enabling a quantitative approach to describe the influence of formulation and processing of a food product on a targeted food property, the latter has to be decided in the context of the question to be answered or the problem to be solved. Food classification aims for supporting the development of dietary guidelines for which the nutrition value NV of a food product is confirmed as key property. In the following a suggested three-step procedure is described for processed food products, treating formulation and processing separately but taking into account their mutual influence on the NV.

5.2.1 Quantification of the nutrition value (step 1)

The so-far well-experienced Nutrition Rich Food Index (NRF_{x.y}) was selected as the exemplary approach to quantify the nutritional value /30, 31, 32/. The NRF_{x.y} is a formulation-related value for nutrition profiling of food products considering the two groups of x recommended nutrients (NR) and y nutrients to be limited (LIM) according to equation 1, below /31/. Typical numbers for x and y are 9 and 3 according to 9 recommended nutrients (NR): protein, dietary fibre, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E, calcium, iron, potassium and magnesium and 3 recommended to be limited nutrients (LIM): added sugar, saturated fatty acids and sodium.

$$\text{NRF}_{9.3_{100 \text{ kcal}}} = \text{NR}_{9_{100 \text{ kcal}}} - \text{LIM}_{3_{100 \text{ kcal}}} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

with: (I) $\text{NR}_{9_{100 \text{ kcal}}} = \sum_{i=1-9} (m_{\text{nutrient } i} / m_{\text{DV}i}) / S_i \cdot 100$ denoting 9 nutrients recommended per serving (weight), $m_{\text{DV}i}$ = mass of Daily Value (nutrient i) and S_i = calories per serving

(ii) $\text{LIM}_{3_{100 \text{ kcal}}} = \sum_{i=1-3} (m_{\text{nutrient } i} / m_{\text{MRV}i}) / S_i \cdot 100$ denoting (3) nutrients to be limited per serving (weight), $m_{\text{MRV}i}$ = mass of maximum recommended value

A logical connection can be seen between nutrient density (ND), energy density (ED) and NRF, since for the basis of a food portion with 100 kcal energy content, only products with high ND or high ED and high ND achieve a high NRF score. Those with (only) high ED or low ND are found in the low NRF score range. NRF_{x.y} also has strengths in terms of its flexible adaptability to the preferred needs of certain consumer groups, as explained in more detail in Chapter 9.1 of the appendix to this report. Consequently, NRF_{x.y} was chosen as the recommended base definition of nutritional value, our selected food property to be classified.

5.2.2 Quantification of degrees of formulation and processing (step 2)

Since the NRFx.y describes the proportions of the nutritionally relevant components of a food formulation, it also represents a nutritional value-related “formulation level” that can be used as a formulation classification parameter (CP). In order to define an equally suitable, easy-to-determine processing parameter, it is suggested to refer to the chosen NRFx.y-based nutrition value definition and express the “degree of processing” by the difference in the NRFx.y value after and before processing treatment, denoted as $\Delta\text{NRFx.y}$, which is subsequently used to classify the influence of processing on the nutrition value (equation 2).

$$\Delta\text{NRFx.y} = \text{NRFx.y}_{\text{after processing}} - \text{NRFx.y}_{\text{before processing}} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

The values x (number of nutrients recommended) and y (number of nutrients to be limited) were chosen as 9 and 3, thus configuring the NRF9.3 as has been described in chapter 5.2.1.

5.2.3 Graphical representation of the IUFoST F&P Classification (IF&PC) approach (step 3)

A 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram is suggested for the graphical representation of (i) the NRF9.3 as quantitative nutrition value-related “formulation level” classification parameter (CP1) and (ii) $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ as quantitative nutrition value-related “processing level” classification parameter (CP2) as demonstrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD) illustrating the Formulation (NRF9.3) and Processing ($\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$) classification parameter space with included Iso-FPFI^N (definition by eq. 3, below) lines, scaled from -10 to +10, enabling re-dimensioned FPF^N-one-parameter classification based on the coupled quantitative impacts of formulation (F) and processing (P) measures. – F & P related examples (apple, carrot and pea product) considered and calculated FPF^N-values visualized (data sources: FNDDS /63/ and /62/); pea protein isolate processing (red arrow) from pea seeds (e.g. by alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation) shows an increase in FPF^N mainly due to the factor 3.5 concentration of protein; other considered processes (pasteurization, baking, cooking) demonstrate FPF^N-reduction due to losses in vitamins

On the x-axis the NRF9.3 is displayed within the range of -100 to +200. Fresh berries and citrus fruits come close to NRF9.3 values of 200 while sugar sweetened soda beverages can reach values below -50 /13/. The processing degree Δ NRF9.3 can impact positively or negatively onto the nutrition value within an estimated maximum range of -100 to +100 based on initial experience. The coupled impact of formulation level (F) expressed by NRF9.3 and processing level (P) expressed by Δ NRF9.3 can be calculated applying equation 3 which defines the so-called Food Processing and Formulation Index FPF^N, the superscript N indicating the nutrition value as the considered food property being classified. Thus, FPF^N values represent quantitative Nutrition Value classes, which are indicated in Figure 6 by Iso-FPF^N lines (lines of constant FPF^N).

$$\text{FPF}^N = [(\text{NRF9.3}_1 + 2\Delta\text{NRF9.3}) / A] - B \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

with A, B denoting scaling constants of the Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD), demonstrated in Fig.6, where A = 25 (1 FPF^N unit equivalency to 25 NRF9.3 units) and B = -2 (FPF^N value in the origo). The subscript 1 represents the NRF9.3 before the considered processing step)

5.2.4 Tracking of formulation & processing in the 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD)

Points located in the CMD are denoted as $P_i (x_i / y_i)$ or $P_i (\text{NRF9.3}_i / \Delta\text{NRF9.3}_i)$, with NRF9.3 being the x-coordinate and Δ NRF9.3 the y-coordinate. A formulation for a food product to be processed before processing is described by a starting point $P_1 (\text{NRF9.3}_1 / 0)$. This starting point P_1 is located on the Δ NRF9.3 (processing scale) zero line. If a pure formulation change is executed (e.g by adding sugar to glaze carrots; see example in Figure 6), this causes a horizontal shift from $P_1 (\text{NRF9.3}_1 / 0)$, to a $P_2 (\text{NRF9.3}_2 / 0)$ in the diagram. With $\text{NRF9.3}_2 < \text{NRF9.3}_1$ due to the LIM-term increase in the NRF9.3 caused by the sugar addition (see eq.1), the shift vector (arrow) is negatively directed.

A processing step that results in a change of the NRF9.3 value from $(\text{NRF9.3})_2$ before processing to $(\text{NRF9.3})_3$ after processing and thus generates a corresponding Δ NRF9.3 (= $(\text{NRF9.3})_3 - (\text{NRF9.3})_2$), causes a point shift from the starting point $P_2 (\text{NRF9.3}_2 / 0)$ to the resulting $P_3 (\text{NRF9.3}_2 + \Delta\text{NRF9.3} / \Delta\text{NRF9.3}_3)$. Thus, P_3 is placed along a straight line (SL) through P_2 inclined (for equidistant scaling units in x and y direction by +45°) relative to the NRF9.3 (x) axis (Fig. 6). If $\text{NRF9.3}_2 > \text{NRF9.3}_3$ then Δ NRF9.3 < 0, a negative impact of the processing step is resulting (see example: glazed carrots cooked; Figure 6), and P_3 is lower left-shifted from P_2 along SL. In case of $\text{NRF9.3}_2 < \text{NRF9.3}_3$ the P_3 shift will be to the upper right along SL (see example: pea protein isolate processing from pea seeds; Figure 6).

For each change in formulation or processing the FPF^N can be calculated according to equation 3. Respective FPF^N values are denoted for the exemplary processed product examples presented within Figure 6.

The FPF^N value shifts between starting- and endpoints correspond to the influence of coupled formulation and processing steps applied in the manufacture of a processed food product one can stepwise follow in the CMD. Which FPF^N value (class) a finally processed food product reaches also depends on the starting point, given by the NRF9.3 of the initial formulation. Starting from base formulations of different NRF_{x.y} (Nutrition Value) and coupling with different processing steps of positive or negative impact could lead to endpoints in the CMD of similar FPF^N values and thus in the same F&P-coupled nutrition value class. A detailed interpretation of such results will also depend on the possible extensions to the NRF9.3 as suggested in the Appendix chapters 9.1.2 and 9.1.3.

The FPF^N values scale from -10 to +10. FPF^N_i and can be calculated according to equation 3 for each point P_i in the CMD. Iso-FPF^N lines have been inserted into the CMD for orientation. These Iso-lines are inclined by -45° to the NRF9.3-axis (for equidistant scaling of both CMD axes) thus being oriented rectangular to the straight SL-lines along which the “processing impact vectors” with a length of $\sqrt{2} \Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ are displayed. The factor $\sqrt{2}$ results from the fact that the processing vector endpoint (e.g. P_3 in Fig. 6) is received from equal shifts of the starting point (e.g. P_2) by $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ (= $(\text{NRF9.3})_3 - (\text{NRF9.3})_2$) into the x and y directions. For each processing

change resulting in a ΔNRF value and related point shift in the diagram from P_i to P_{i+1} the FPFI^{N} in the endpoint P_{i+1} is received from equation 3 (for further details see Appendix chapter 9.1.4).

5.2.5 Key benefits in applying the 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD)

The CMD has been created in order to support the practical application of the two separated and quantified levels of formulation (F) and processing (P) impacts on the nutrition value (NV). As expected, such quantifying two-parameter classification system initially places increased demands on handling compared to only qualitatively descriptive or partially quantifying single-parameter systems.

As the exemplary (apple, carrot and pea) demonstration of formulation changes and processing modifications in Chapter 5.2.4 and Figure 6 demonstrate, practical handling for the two-parameter IF&PC approach can be well assisted by the CMD. Moreover, the quantitative F&P coupling parameter FPFI^{N} (Food Processing and Formulation Index) as depicted in the CMD indicates a simplified base for possible future consumer communication and product labelling approaches considering F and P aspects appropriately. For assistance in refining the NOVA classification systems it may be advantageous to apply the NRF9.3 (or modifications of it introduced as $\text{NRF}^{\text{x.y.z}}$ in chapter 9.1 in the Appendix to this report) as quantitative formulation characteristics and $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ (or respective modifications $\Delta\text{NRF}^{\text{x.y.z}}$) separately, or in the coupled FPFI^{N} format, for the NOVA-specific correlations with obesity and related health risk outcomes. - Main handling rules and resulting benefits in applying the CMD are summarized in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Handling rules and determined parameter-info by the CMD application

Nr	Criterion	Handling	Benefits (CMD)
1	Starting with a formulation	Calculate the NRF9.3_1 and place starting point P_1 ($\text{NRF9.3}_1 / 0$) on the $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ zero line	Initial formulation-based nutrition value determined and visualized
2	Pure formulation change	Calculate new NRF9.3_2 and insert point P_2 ($\text{NRF9.3}_2 / 0$) on the $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ zero line.	Horizontal shift from P_1 to P_2 on $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$ zero line indicates the nutrition quality change due to the formulation modification
3	Processing treatment application	Calculate $\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$, insert point P_3 ($\text{NRF9.3}_3/\Delta\text{NRF9.3}$) in CMD and calculate FPFI^{N} by eq. 3	Shift length ($\sqrt{2} \Delta\text{NRF9.3}$) of P_2 to P_3 along $+45^\circ$ inclined line (SL) through P_2 ; denotes the processing impact on NV Resulting FPFI^{N} indicates the coupled formulation and processing impact on the nutrition value NV

5.2.6 Extensions of the application frame

There is a range of desirable extensions of the IUFOST Formulation & Processing Classification (IF&PC) approach. These concern aspects of (a) considering other or further nutrients, (b) weighing nutrients included in the $\text{NRF}^{\text{x.y}}$ differently, (c) including additional nutrients or nutrient groups which are influenced by processing treatments leading to their reduction or increase and (d) introduce additional food matrix function criteria of nutritional relevance which may also be influenced by processing. In table 3 a detailed overview on these extension aspects (a-d) is given, including contextual measures taken, being under exploration or of future research interest. A more detailed overview of IF&PC-based extensions on application scenarios for different consumer groups and additional categories of processing treatments is given in chapter 9.1 of the Report Appendix. The exploration of relevant formulation and processing step combinations is expected to complement part of future project work for refinement and validation of the introduced IUFOST Formulation and Processing Classification (IF&PC) scheme with its 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD) tool. Main future requirements will be (i) the acquisition of nutrient data for ingredients and food components before and after processing as

well as (ii) the identification of processes or processing steps to be specifically considered in the classification. Related challenges and opportunities are expected in this context for modified definitions of the NRF to extend the application range of the IF&PC approach (see Appendix, chapter 9.1).

Table 3: Suggested extensions of the IF&PC scheme & expected measures / benefits concerning a more holistic description of F& P impacts on the nutrition value (NV)

Nr	Extension-Aspect	Suggested considerations	Expected Benefits (CMD)
(a)	Wider ranges of nutrients recommended (NR) and to be limited (LIM)	Extending the NRF9.3 to NR ($x > 9$), LIM ($y > 3$); partially already applied; e.g. /58/)	Improved fit for consumer groups with specific nutrient requirements
(b)	Different weighing of specific nutrients / nutrient groups (NR, LIM)	Giving different weights to specific nutrients by introducing nutrient or nutrient group (NR, LIM) specific weighing factors a_i into the $NRF_{x,y}$ (addressed by some authors e.g. /57/)	Adaptability for consumer groups or individuals (personalization) with specific nutrient requirements
(c)	Consideration of ingredients /components of relevant impact on the nutrition value (NV) which can be influenced (reduced or activated / generated) by processing	<p>Inclusion of the groups of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (z_1) antinutrients to be inactivated (i.e.: phytate, tannins, trypsin inhibitor, polyphenols) (z_2) contaminants to be extracted or neutralized (z_3) components to be treated for improving their digestibility (i.e. proteins, starches,...) <p>To follow the suggested IF&PC scheme approach such components / ingredient groups will have to be represented in the $NRF_{x,y,z_1...z_N}$ and the related $\Delta NRF_{x,y,z_1...z_N}$ and being determined by analyses before and after processing steps.</p> <p>(suggested & conceptually pre-explored by IUFOST task force, see Appendix chapter 9.1)</p>	<p>Processing induced <u>reduction</u> of $z_1...z_N$ will enable improving the nutrition value (increase in modified $NRF_{x,y,z_1...z_N}$).</p> <p>This will enter into a negative term within $NRF_{x,y,z_1...z_N}$ and $\Delta NRF_{x,y,z_1...z_N}$, z-component reduction increasing these.</p> <p>Thus, in a CMD the calculated $\Delta NRF_{x,y,z}$ processing vector would be directed upper-right along a $+45^\circ$ oriented straight line (SL) relative to the x- ($NRF_{x,y,z}$) axis.</p> <p>The $FPFI^N$ of the endpoint in the CMD is shifted towards increased values (green zone directed). This is expected to enable demonstration of a series of positive processing impact mechanisms relevant for the NV.</p>
(d)	Consideration of food Matrix effects on digestion and nutrient release kinetics	<p>(z_4) Introduction of a kinetics factor term as processing dependent weighing factor for nutrients the release kinetics of which is of relevance for digestibility, bio-accessibility & bioavailability as well as related satiation kinetics.</p> <p>(suggested by IUFOST task-force, see report Appendix chapter 9.1.2 and 9.1.3)</p>	<p>This is expected to newly add kinetics aspects into nutrition value (NV) description. It is seen as crucial if eating and digestion-related phenomena shall be taken into account which are time-dependent</p> <p>In the context of this report the food uptake kinetics (eating speed/frequency) & its relation to digestion and "satiation" kinetics is of major interest to better understand consumers "overeating" behaviour, a key factor for obesity and related health risk outcomes.</p> <p>Research and development work in this thematic domain is highly recommended.</p>

6. Recommendations

This chapter is meant to extract part of the toolbox elements which have been developed by the IUFoST task force for differentiation and quantification of formulation and processing impacts on the nutrition value, in order to suggest the application of such elements for refinement of the NOVA classification system. In this context further exemplary literature supporting the NOVA classification (e.g. /33/-/38/) and such that takes a critical position (e.g. /39/-/48/) is considered.

6.1 NOVA Refinement suggestions

The proposed steps to refine the NOVA classification system aim to eliminate ambiguities and inaccuracies that were identified by the task force and further analysed with regard to their NOVA-based causes. Table 4 provides an overview of the results of these analyses and the proposed measures derived from these.

TABLE 4: NOVA analysis-based identification of refinement measures

Nr.	ambiguities / inaccuracies	NOVA-intrinsic sources	suggested measures	chapter
1	confusion of formulation and processing	S1. discrepancy between nature of classification parameters and designation of classes S2. vague and over-inclusive definition of UPF S3. no clear focus on nutrition value (e.g for specific “UPF-ingredients”)	M1. clear definition, differentiation & separation of formulation & processing M2. reference to nutrition value as 1 st target property for M1 measures M3. in future: consider formulation & processing parameter(s) impact on palatability & satiation kinetics aspects as 2 nd /3 rd target properties (including aspects of e.g.: matrix volume, water & air content, H ₂ O-binding in modified NRF*)	5.1
2	missing quantification of formulation and processing parameters	S4. restriction to qualitative characterization of food products (no thresholds for formulation, no levels of formulation and processing)	M4. quantifying levels of formulation (i.e. NRF ^{*x.y.z}) & processing (i.e. ΔNRF ^{*x.y.z}) M5. enabling coupling of F- & P-parameters (e.g. FPF ^{I^N}) to simplify M6. in future: consideration of (i) matrix volume & water/air fractions incl. their change by processing (e.g drying/aeration/gelling); (ii) gastro-intestinal rheology	5.2
3	weak evidence base (observational studies) for correlations between food classes & obesity / health risks	S5. no clear control of other risk factors for weight gain S6. risk of misclassification (i.e. single ingredient dependency for UPF)	M7. base correlations with obesity & health risks on quantified F&P parameters taking nutrition value (& prospectively satiation kinetics) into account	A9,1,2 & A9,1,3

In Chapter 4 a detailed analysis of the NOVA classification system by the task force, assisted by numerous publications has been presented and discussed and NOVA intrinsic sources of ambiguities and inaccuracies have been identified. These findings are summed up in abbreviated form within the first two columns of Table 4.

For the suggested refinement measures presented in column 3 of Table 4 the base for measures M1, M2, M4 and M5 are described by the IF&PC scheme within Chapter 5 of this report. Measures M3 and M5 of future perspective concern a suggested 2nd (and/or 3rd) property besides the nutrition value to be considered. Since the NOVA classification system reasons strongly about the palatability of a food product and related overeating by the consumer, the “Satiating Kinetics Potential (SKP)” is recommended as such 2nd target property. A first related

parameter relevant for consideration in the modified $NRF^{*x.y.z}$ could be the calorie-specific food matrix volume. This is strongly dependent on (i) water content and water binding characteristics of the food product which in turn is expected to significantly influence the filling degree and residence time in the gastric volume upon eating as well as (ii) on the rheology of the gastric content. $NRF^{*x.y.z}$ could consider a related volume-parameter term and processing can largely impact on such e.g by drying or concentration (volume and water content reduction) or water incorporation supported by gelling/thickening (volume and water content / water binding increase).

This is an attempt for suitable parameter selection but still far from comprehensively covering the satiation / overeating / obesity relationships in all their complexity. However, this approach can be seen as a first prospective step towards the extended application of the IF&PC scheme for another target property (Satiation Kinetics Potential) of processed foods, which, in addition to the Nutrition Value (NV) influences obesity and related health risks. This approach could therefore be understood as a future complementary step into a refinement procedure for the NOVA classification system using the IF&PC scheme as efficient tool.

Figure 7 : Coupling of NOVA system with the suggested IF&PC system approach for NOVA refinement and completion to a classification system taking differentiated and quantified formulation and processing parameters into account, based on which the NOVA correlations with obesity and health risk outcomes could be improved. Positioning of suggested NOVA refinement measures M1-M7 (table 4) within a coupled IF&PC & NOVA (IUVA) approach (prospective measures in brackets).

Hence, the IF&PC scheme would enable refining the NOVA classification base at the point of purchase (POP) based on which the NOVA system could then build its intended food impact correlation with obesity and related health risk data. $NRF^{*x.y.z}$ for the formulation level and $\Delta NRF^{*x.y.z}$ for the processing level or $FPFI^N$ as recoupled formulation and processing level would thus be applied as quantitative classification base parameters – Such synergistic IF&PC-NOVA connection denoted here as suggested IUFoST- refined NOVA (IUVA) approach is schematically demonstrated in Figure 7.

Summarizing this chapter, the IUFoST task force is of the opinion that the application of the IF&PC scheme will have the potential to bring the following improvements to the NOVA system, which will in turn assist in eliminating ambiguities and uncertainties that exist up to now:

- (1) Clear separation of formulation and processing influences on the nutritional value of processed foods
- (2) Quantification of levels of formulation and processing influences
- (3) From (1) and (2) provision of a quantitative food product classification base to apply

- either separate F & P levels or quantitatively recoupled F & P levels expressed by the nutrition value-related (superscript N) Formulation and Processing Food Index $F\text{PFI}^N$ as classification parameters.
- (4) Use of the classification base according to (3) for improved correlative comparison with data on obesity and associated health risks (Food Impact Correlation)
 - (5) Differentiating conclusions on F & P or $F\text{PFI}^N$ influences with regard to determined food impact correlation results according to (4)
 - (6) Indicated possibility of extended considerations for processed foods by including other product properties in addition to the nutritional value (e.g.: satiation kinetics and palatability in the NOVA context, but as well sustainability, safety, convenience and affordability; see chapter 7) and their handling according to the IF&PC scheme.
 - (7) Further improvement of the classification base for processed foods at the point of Purchase (POP) in accordance with (6) for appropriate quantitative use in further refined correlation analyses according to (4)
 - (8) Iterative refinement of the classification and correlation procedures according to steps (1)-(7), applying appropriately extended classification parameters for levels of formulation ($\text{NRF}^{\text{x.y.z}}$) and processing ($\Delta\text{NRF}^{\text{x.y.z}}$) which consider quantitative digestion and metabolic response characteristics, thus refining food impact correlations with health/health risk data to finally derive evidence-based causal functional relationships.

As a final remark to this chapter, it is important to remember that nearly a billion people do not meet their nutritional needs in the world today. Many living in the developing world. The provision of nutrient-dense foods in such populations is only possible by the inclusion of processed foods. This highlights the need to clearly define the concept of processing and formulation, as the NOVA system has introduced ambiguities that have led to confusion among many who have attempted to apply it, or even caused rejection of the inclusion of processed foods in meeting the nutritional needs of a healthy population.

6.2 R&D requirements in food science / engineering and nutrition

(a) Systematic studies should consider interactions between food components / ingredients and processes and quantify NRF and $\Delta\text{R}\text{NRF}$ values systematically following the IF&PC scheme approach. These should also be carried out for serially arranged processing steps. Food data bases should be complemented by such data sets for processed foods / food components considering different processing intensities without mixing such up with variations in formulation.

(b) The IF&PC scheme should be systematically checked and validated based on various formulation and processing scenarios and modifications/improvements be implemented.

(c) Complementary studies should look at interactions between additives and processes and also study matrix effects impacting on nutrient release and digestion kinetics. A comprehensive literature already exists on several ingredients and additives, and for most of these the totality of evidence does not support harmful health effects. Such additives should not be part of a novel classification system. By contrast, evidence used to develop current authoritative guidelines supports recommendations on nutrients and food components of public health concern, which varies by country, but can include adequacy of certain nutrients (e.g. fiber or calcium) as well as nutrients and food components to limit (e.g. added sugars, *trans* fatty acids, sodium) and these criteria should be included.

(d) Harmful processes and additives should be identified. A revised definition of “Formulation or Process-Induced Health Risk Foods” (FI-HRF; PI-HRF) needs to start with the identification of the harmfulness of processing treatments and/or single, specific ingredients using reliable health biomarkers, and by conducting dose–response relations to identify thresholds.

(e) An international balanced panel of experts from food science/engineering, nutrition, and medicine should be gathered to draft the future IF&PC/NOVA (“IUVA”) food classification version, and subsequently there should be a hearing phase to receive suggestions for

improvements. The panel should also produce a research plan for studies that needs to have its usefulness confirmed before being launched. Such a research plan should involve animal studies, mechanistic human studies, observational studies, and randomized controlled trials. Clear criteria for positive study outcomes should be defined, as well as the totality of evidence required to endorse the further launch of "IUVA".

(f) Close R&D collaborations between food science, food engineering, biological chemistry, clinical nutrition, public health and toxicology researchers and those involved in regulatory and quality sciences should be encouraged and setup addressing the before-mentioned thematic areas (a)-

(e). Such collaborations should also include industrial partners (food producers, food processing developers, and equipment manufacturers).

7. Transferability of the IF&PC Approach

As introduced and discussed throughout this report, the core of the IUFoST Formulation and Processing Classification approach (IF&PC) is the separation and quantification of formulation and processing impacts on the exemplarily selected Nutrition Value as the most relevant food property parameter underlaid to the NOVA classification system. The extended Nutrition Rich Food Index $NRF^{*x.y.z}$ and its difference between food product states before and after a processing treatment ($\Delta NRF^{*x.y.z}$) were successfully pre-validated as suitable Classification Parameters (CP) for quantitative formulation and processing impacts. This sub-chapter intends to demonstrate the prospective generalizability of this approach with respect to other food product characteristics than the nutrition value. As addressed in Chapter 3.2.1 further food product properties of consumer relevance are: safety, sustainability, palatability, convenience and affordability. To apply the IF&PC scheme representatively, the property-related classification parameters (CPs) have to be selected at first. Table 5 suggests CPs for the named food product properties.

Table 5: Suggested classification parameters for major (1-6) and specific (7,8) consumer relevant food product properties

Nr	Product Property (PP)	Formulation (F)	Processing (P)	F&P Coupling
1	Nutrition Value	e.g. $NRF^{*x.y.z}$	$\Delta NRF^{*x.y.z}$	$FPF ^{IN}$
2	Sustainability	e.g. Global Warming Potential GWP	ΔGWP (Global Warming Potential Difference)	$FPF ^{SU}$
3	Palatability	e.g. Sensory Score SS Energy Consumption to reach satiation EC-Sat Volume Consumption to reach satiation VC-Sat	ΔSS $\Delta EC-Sat$ $\Delta VC-Sat$	$FPF ^{SS}$ $FPF ^{EC-Sat}$ $FPF ^{VC-Sat}$
4	Safety	e.g. Colony Forming Unit (CFU) count	ΔCFU	$FPF ^{CFU}$
5	Convenience	e.g. Convenience Score CS	ΔCS	$FPF ^{CS}$
6	Affordability	e.g. Energy Consumption / \$ or $NRF^{*x.y.z}/\$$	$\Delta EC\$$ $\Delta NRF/\$$; $\Delta NRF^{*}/\$$	$FPF ^{EC\$}$ $FPF ^{NRF\$}$ $FPF ^{NRF^{*}\$}$
7	Digestibility: e.g. for proteins further static or dynamic (future) INFOGEST (IG) parameters $P_1 \dots P_N$	e.g. PDCAAS* DIAAS**	$\Delta PDCAAS$ $\Delta DIAAS$	$FPF ^{PDCAAS}$ $FPF ^{DIAAS}$
8		e.g. IG-Pi	$\Delta IG-Pi$	$FPF ^{IGPi}$

(*PDCAAS = Protein Digestibility Corrected Amino Acid Score; "DIAAS = ratio of digestible amino acid content in the food (mg/g of protein) to the same amino acid in a reference pattern taken from age-specific amino acid requirements; INFOGEST = in vitro simulation of gastrointestinal food digestion)

Nr.1 in Table 5 represents the case treated in detail within this report. In some of the product properties like 1 (Nutrition Value), 3 (Palatability), 4 (Safety), 5 (Convenience), and 7 (Digestibility), the processing is known to allow for improvements. However, improvement in one of these may cause trade-offs for another ones.

For Nr. 2 (Sustainability) processing will, in general, add an additional negative load. However different ways of processing can be differentiated, and the least burdensome process can be identified and selected.

For Nr.6 (affordability) processing costs are adding, however the resulting product could be cheaper due to concentration effects impacting positively e.g. on transport costs and nutritional effects (e.g. satiation efficiency, nutritional energy supply efficiency) the latter may be of specific relevance in developing countries but also in domains like sports nutrition.

Nr. 7 (Digestibility) is seen as key part of a promising development which is expected to lead to more evidence-based correlations and finally to functional relationship insights between the quality of food products at the point of purchase (POP) and digestion as well as metabolic response characteristics, which in turn will provide a quantitative base for next step correlations and functional dependency derivations concerning obesity and related health risk aspects.

Thus, the IF&PC scheme suggested by this report is expected having the potential to pave the way for an appropriate prospective consideration of processing impacts on food product quality in a holistic manner. For such a holistic approach, which will enable addressing a number of quality criteria Q_i for formulated and processed food products, the obvious question is whether an associated multi-parameter classification can still be communicated to the consumer. In this regard, it will generally be possible to use a coding system (e.g. QR) to call up the classification results for various quality criteria Q_1 to Q_n of a product and to clearly visualize related scores. The weighting of the various Q_i should be left to the discretion of the product developers and ultimately the consumers.

8. Conclusions

The international task force on Food Processing for Nutrition, Diet and Health, established by the International Union of Food Science and Technology (IUFoST) has constructively worked out a rational approach to define the impact of food processing on the nutritional value of processed food products, referred to as IUFoST Formulation and Processing Classification (IF&PC) scheme.

8.1 Refinement of the NOVA classification system

The initial key purpose was to assist in the refinement and improvement of the NOVA classification concept by addressing the confusion between formulation and processing and the non-quantitative assessment in the NOVA system. This has expanded globally and is used by the general public although the definition or meaning of the phrase as used by the general public is not always clear nor are the criteria for identification of foods included in the "ultra-processed" category explicitly or quantitatively defined. The frequently heard argument that NOVA represents a simple classification system is offset by the difficulty of its application due to described ambiguities and unquantified assessment criteria.

Nevertheless, the task force is of the opinion that the NOVA system has included processing as a significant influencing factor on the nutritional properties of processed food products into the classification of such products which has so far not been sufficiently considered.

Accordingly, the task force finally favoured a problem-solution methodology addressing a six-step approach consisting of:

- (i) identification of the target food property to be addressed (= nutrition value in the NOVA context)
- (ii) differentiation of formulation (F) and processing (P),
- (iii) quantification of levels (= classes) for F and P,
- (iv) developing a simple representation scheme for the two-parameter (F&P) classification,
- (v) rational consolidation into a coupled F&P one-parameter (FPFI^N) classification and
- (vi) derivation of refinement suggestions for the NOVA system (chapter 6.1).

This approach configures the IUFOST Formulation and Processing Classification (IF&PC) scheme.

Hence the NOVA system can apply this scheme to quantitatively classify processed food products at the point of purchase, in order to then follow the NOVA-specific “food impact correlation” with obesity and related health risk data. – This should allow for eliminating the so far governing ambiguities and confusion in applying the NOVA-type approach.

8.2 General applicability of the IF&PC scheme

Besides the task force work result for the NOVA refinement there is another outcome of overarching interest. As identified by the task force the IF&PC scheme has future potential to be transferred for the consideration of other targeted food properties than the nutrition value purposely selected for the NOVA classification refinement.

Such food properties of major relevance are: (a) safety, (b) sustainability, (c) palatability, (d) affordability and (e) convenience. Digestibility (f) and (g) metabolic response could also be added e.g. in case of motivation for a further refinement step to be addressed to NOVA’s food-obesity-health risk correlation approach.

For all of the main food properties named before (a)-(g) one can explore differentiated property-specific formulation (F) and processing (P) classification parameters, derive a two parameter (F&P) classification and consolidate to a one-parameter (FPFI^x) classification.

Such holistic approach creates a quantifiable basis for the realistic development of food products, which usually also have to take into account other product properties in addition to the nutritional value.

For both scenarios, the NOVA System refinement (8.1) and the consideration of several essential food product properties (8.2), there are demanding future R&D and industrial application requirements which relate to the systematic acquisition of data (classification parameters CP, e.g. NRF_{x.y.z} and Δ NRF_{x.y.}) for food product formulations before and after execution of processing steps.

Such data will support research on the IF&PC scheme application in a wider food product framework to validate and refine the scheme. Related investigations should include all suggested food properties of major relevance.

In order to successfully manage accessing and orchestrating the required interdisciplinary expertise, the IUFOST task force highly recommends to the communities of food scientists, food engineers, and nutrition scientists and related professional as they are, e.g., represented by IUFOST and IUNS to join forces and encourage concerted international R&D actions.

9. APPENDIX

9.1 Extension options for the IF&PC concept

In addition to the statements made in chapter 5.2.6 extension approaches for definitions of NRF and Δ NRF will be addressed in this chapter and conceptually substantiated. Since most of the suggested extensions still require approval based on experimental data which may not yet be available in the scientific literature and food product data bases, this will require concerted action of food scientists', food engineers' and nutritionists' communities, explicitly recommended. The extension of application ranges for the introduced IF&PC scheme approach aims for adaptability of the NRF as formulation base parameter to different consumer groups and their specific needs. Accordingly, also Δ NRF as the corresponding processing impact parameter will follow such extension for various processing categories which impact positively or negatively on the food property in focus for classification (here: nutrition value NV).

9.1.1 Colour-code complement

First, a colour code addition to the 2D (F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD, introduced in Chapter 5.2.3) is presented. This is a possible option to more clearly represent the FPF^N domains, which could be considered for a simplified evaluation by the consumer. The positioning of the FPF^N values and the corresponding colour code values in Figure A1 follow the arbitrary assumption that the NRF9.3 value at the NRF scale centre (x-axis), represented by NRF9.3 = 50, determines the mean of the FPF^N scale with FPF^N=0 without super-imposed processing and the corresponding yellow colour mean (see yellow diamond symbol for assistance).

Figure A1: 2D-(F&P) Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD) illustrating the Formulation (NRF9.3) and Processing (Δ NRF9.3) classification parameter space with included FPF^N related colour scheme, and included Iso-FPF^N lines, enabling re-dimensioned one-parameter classification, based on the coupled quantitative impacts of formulation (F) and processing (P) measures. – F&P related examples (apple, carrot and pea) considered and calculated FPF^N-values displayed. (data sources: FNDDS data base /63/ and /62/); pea protein isolate processing from pea seeds (e.g. by alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation) shows an increase in FPF^N mainly due to the factor 3.5 concentration of protein; other considered processes (baking pasteurization, cooking) demonstrate FPF^N-reduction due to losses in vitamins.

9.1.2 Extended definition of the NRF_{x.y} (nutrition value related quantitative formulation level)

To address the question of whether the chosen NRF_{x.y}-related criteria describing the nutrition value of a processed food could be expanded to a wider scope of applications covering different nutrition scenarios of consumers (a) in industrialised and developing countries, (b) for different consumer groups (e.g. infant, elderly, pregnant women) and (c) even broken down to an individual consumer level (e.g. with different BMI or personalized characteristics), possibilities to adaptively modify the definitions of NRF_{9.3} and ΔNRF_{9.3} were explored.

Accordingly, on top of the more obvious possibility to integrate different numbers and candidates of recommended (NR) and/or to be limited (LIM) nutrients into the NRF_{x.y}, weighing factors a_i can be implemented for the two summing terms of the NRF_{x.y} (NR, LIM) as shown in equation A1. A further extension option introducing such weighing factors also for single nutrients in the NR and LIM terms are demonstrated by eq. A2.

$$\text{NRF}^*_{x.y} \text{ 100kcal} = a_1 \text{NR}^*_{x} \text{ 100kcal} - a_2 \text{LIM}^*_{y} \text{ 100kcal} \quad (\text{eq. A1})$$

$$\text{NRF}^*_{x.y} \text{ 100kcal} = \sum_{1-9} [(a_{1,i} m_{\text{nutrient } i} / m_{\text{DVi}}) + \sum_{1-3} [(a_{2,i} m_{\text{nutrient } i} / m_{\text{MRVi}})] / S_i \cdot 100 \quad (\text{eq. A2})$$

Such extended NRF_{x.y} are subsequently marked by a superscript star symbol as NRF^{*}_{x.y}.

9.1.3 Extended definition of ΔNRF_{x.y} (nutrition value related quantitative processing level)

In case respective ΔNRF_{x.y} or ΔNRF^{*}_{x.y} values were used to capture the processing impact on the nutrition value of a food product according to the NRF definitions in equations 1, A1 or A2, this would only enable considering nutrients included in the NR or LIM terms partially or fully disappearing or enriching as a consequence of the processing treatment. However, there are other possible processing impacts of relevance on the nutrition value of food products the IF&PC approach intends to be prepared for appropriate consideration. Such are e.g. (i) inactivation of anti-nutrients, (ii) reduction/avoidance of process-induced generation of unwanted substances and (iii) food matrix structure modification, but not restricted to these.

The prominent example described in more detail below relates to the inactivation of anti-nutrients, like phytate or phytic acid causing problems in many people because of their mineral-binding and enzyme blocking effects /49-53/. Consequently, the partial or complete inactivation of such anti-nutrients is recommended.

Thus, an extended consideration of processing impacts on the nutrition value by the ΔNRF^{*} parameter could include a third Δ-term for antinutrient inactivation (ΔAN_z or ΔAN^{*}_z) as demonstrated in equation A4. However, this also requires an appropriate consideration of an antinutrient term in the NRF^{*} denoted as AN^{*}_z accordingly demonstrated by equation A3.

$$\text{NRF}^*_{x.y.z} \text{ 100kcal} = \text{NR}^*_{x} \text{ 100kcal} - \text{LIM}^*_{y} \text{ 100kcal} - \text{AN}^*_{z} \text{ 100kcal} \quad (\text{eq. A3})$$

$$\Delta \text{NRF}^*_{x.y.z} \text{ 100kcal} = \Delta \text{NR}^*_{x} \text{ 100kcal} - \Delta \text{LIM}^*_{y} \text{ 100kcal} - \Delta \text{AN}^*_{z} \text{ 100kcal} \quad (\text{eq. A4})$$

with:

$$\text{AN}^*_{z \text{ 100 kcal}} = \sum_{1-z} (m_{\text{antinutrient } i} / m_{\text{MTi}}) / S_i \cdot 100 \quad (\text{eq. A5})$$

where m_{MTi} denotes the maximum tolerated mass of the considered anti-nutrient and S_i stands for calories / serving. 100 kcal could also be replaced by 418.4 kJ to adapt to SI-units.

For the NRF^{*}_{x.y.z} and ΔNRF^{*}_{x.y.z} extended in this way, the x,y,z represent the numbers of nutrients recommended (x), nutrients to be limited (y) and of anti-nutrients to be inactivated (z). In the following NRF^{*}_{9.3.1} and ΔNRF^{*}_{9.3.1} were further explored. Weighing factors introduced in chapter 9.1.1 can also be considered for the anti-nutrients (e.g. denoted as $a_{3,i}$).

Further anti-nutrient candidates besides phytic acid or phytate which could be relevant for consideration, are tannins, other polyphenolic components and trypsin inhibitor. Figure A2 demonstrates the impact of phytic acid/phytate inactivation (a) in processing of dry pea seed, applying alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation (denotation 1) to produce a pea protein isolate and (b) in subsequent high moisture extrusion and autoclaving (denotation 2) to manufacture a meat analogue based on such pea protein isolate. Calculated $NRF^{*9.3.1}_{100kcal}$ and $\Delta NRF^{*9.3.1}_{100kcal}$ (eq. A3-A5) consider the partial phytate inactivation (red and white arrows in fig. A2). In order to demonstrate the impact of the phytic acid inactivation consideration, $NRF_{9.3}$ and $\Delta NRF_{9.3}$ which do not consider this inactivation aspect, are also plotted in fig. A2 for the alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation processing (denotation 3, blue arrow in fig. A2). This comparison indicates that (i) the NRF starting points on the 0-processing line ($\Delta NRF=0$) are shifted by the value of the (negative) AN1-term (eqs. A3 and A5), (ii) the phytic acid inactivation, in addition to the positive protein concentration shift the endpoint of processing step (1) by extraction & precipitation to a higher $FPFIN^N$ value than resulting for the same process (3) but without consideration of the phytic acid inactivation and (iii) the gain in $FPFIN^N$ for close to complete phytate inactivation after extrusion and autoclaving by process (2) approximately equals the $FPFIN$ shift of the starting points considered in (i). Accordingly, this example supports the extension of the $NRF_{9.3}$ and $\Delta NRF_{9.3}$ by "impact terms" for processing influences on relevant nutrients or nutrient groups contributing to the nutrition value of a processed food product.

Figure A2: CMD plot demonstrating the influence of phytate/phytic acid inactivation in pea through meat analogue processing, from pea seed to pea protein isolate to extruded/autoclaved protein isolate based product, if considered by the extended $NRF^{*9.3.1}$ and $\Delta NRF^{*9.3.1}$; comparison with $NRF_{9.3}$ versus $\Delta NRF_{9.3}$ plot neglecting phytate/phytic acid inactivation; 8processing steps 1 & 3: alkaline extraction and isoelectric precipitation of pea protein isolate from seeds; step 2: pea protein isolate extrusion and autoclaving); detailed data in Table A1

Table 1 provides quantitative phytate data for the processed pea seed and pea protein isolate materials presented in figure A2. For calculating the AN1 term (eq. A5) a value for the maximum tolerated mass ($m_{MT_{\text{phyt}}}$) of the considered anti-nutrient (here: phytic acid/phytate) had to be fixed. Based on literature data /49, 50/ we set the $m_{MT_{\text{phyt}}}$ to 10 mg/100g which should enable > 50% of relative Fe absorption as demonstrated by figure A2 below.

Table A1: Antinutrient (phytate) inactivation in pea seed / pea protein isolate processing as exemplary IF&PC extension case /59-65/.

$z = 1$ (phytate (P))
 $S_i = 367$ kcal/100g (PPI-based meat analogue);
 m_{MT_i} (phytase) = 10 mg/100g = 2.72 mg/100 kcal (ca. $\geq 50\%$ of relative Fe absorption; /50/ and Figure A2)

PEA (dried):	Phytate mg/100g	AN1 (eq. A5)	NRF* _{9.3.1} (eq. A3)	Δ NRF* _{9.3.1} (eq. A4)	FPFIN* _{9.3.1} (eq. 3)	NRF _{9.3} (eq. 1)	Δ NRF _{9.3} (eq. 2)	FPFIN* _{9.3} (eq. 3)
raw (seeds)-max	1200	32.70	22.66			55.36		
protein isolate-max	200	5.45	76.70	54.04	+3.23	82.15	26.79	+2.36
extruded & autoclaved and/or phytase treated pea protein isolate	10	0.25	81.90	5.20	+3.64	82.15	0.00	-

Figure A3 provides information to reason for the selected threshold value $m_{MT1} = 10$ mg Phytic Acid (PA) / 100g food product (equivalent to ca. 5.05 mg/100 kcal for pea protein isolate based meat analogue with 198 kcal/100g of energy density).

Figure A3: Increase in relative iron absorption for phytic acid (PA) reduction /49, 50, 60/ (here: target threshold: 10 mg PA/100 g food product to reach $\geq 50\%$ relative absorption of iron (Fe) from naturally iron containing or fortified food products (adapted from R. Hurrell et. al. /50/).

9.1.4 Combinations of formulation and processing steps

The manufacture of processed food products may typically include several formulation / re-formulation and processing steps. Within this Appendix-subchapter we demonstrate the suitability in applying the F&P Classification Matrix Diagram (CMD) introduced in chapter 5.2.3 for quantitative description and clear representation of such multi-step F&P applications. In nutrition data bases data for food products before and after distinct processing steps for the same formulation are so far rarely found. Accordingly, the following demonstration of coupled multiple-formulation and processing steps applying the introduced CMD is of semi-quantitative

nature. However, future systematic analyses of nutrient composition before and after distinct processing steps will allow for closing such data gap efficiently.

Figure A4: Qualitative CMD-representation of coupled formulation (F) and processing (P) steps impacting on the color-coded F&P nutrition value parameter $FPFI^N$

For the fruit system based example demonstrated in figure A4 the food portion base has been set to 100 g because concentration processing of a fresh fruit juice or fruit sauce without added sugars leads in general to a stronger increase of the NR9- compared to the LIM3-term in the NRF9.3 and $\Delta NRF9.3$ (eqs. 1, 2) and thus to an increase in $FPFI^N$. For the 100 kcal base, concentration processing will in general not allow for an increase in $FPFI^N$, because the reduction of the water content by concentration processing contributes to a relative weight change but is calorie neutral. Figure A4 further demonstrates the ease of differentiation between quantitative impacts on the nutrition value through formulation (indicated by horizontal vectors into positive or negative NRF9.3 axis direction) and quantitative processing impacts on the nutrition value (vectors in $+45^\circ$ direction; to upper-right positive, to lower-left negative impacts). For the addition of vitamins and minerals (white arrow) it is of importance to state that this has to be consistent with government policies (e.g. for applications in food fortification) and should not be misused to correct inadequate processing or initial formulation

Processing impacts on the F&P coupling parameter $FPFI^N$ are purposefully given factor 2 stronger weight in the CMD by definition, as indicated in equation 3. This is justified by the fact that processing influences have a gradual effect on the nutrient composition and therefore we recommend such amplification in the representation, whereas formulation influences have a priori step function characteristics. Such relationships will have to be validated based on multiple processed product application experience. In case of extensions of the NRF9.3 suggested in this report (e.g. Appendix chapters 9.1.2 and 9.1.3) one may derive other conclusions on the adaptation of a weighing ratio between formulation and processing impacts.

Thus, the IF&PC approach should be seen as an inspiring starting point with a first set of tools in a toolbox to be worked with and to be systematically extended and improved based on gained experience and the generation of appropriate data sets. This will require a mid to long-term committed interplay between experts in food science, food engineering, human nutrition and nutrition medicine as concluded in further detail within chapter 8 of the report.

10. References

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